

Tiara Afdalia

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Reading Comprehension

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SELF-PACED LEARNING

Reading Comprehension Strategy for Getting and Remembering The Gist of It

Tiara Afdalia
A Student at IAIN Palangka Raya, Indonesia

Topic Detail

Course contents

- 01 **Introduction** Free
Writers write for a reason: They have a specific idea they want to convey. Good writers use facts and other kinds of evidence to support their ideas.
- 02 **Finding the Main Idea** Free
Finding and understanding the main idea of a text is an essential reading skill. This chapter will show you how to distinguish the main idea from its support.
- 03 **Finding the Supporting Ideas** Free
This chapter explains the types of support writers use. You'll also learn how to distinguish between major and minor supporting ideas, which will help you focus on what to remember.
- 04 **Highlighting, Underlining, and Glossing** Free
When you have a lot to read and a lot to remember, three active reading strategies will help you focus on the most information that's most important. This chapter will show you how to effectively highlight, underline, and gloss what you read.
- 05 **Taking Notes and Outlining** Free
Now that you're getting good at finding main and supporting ideas, you can begin to write effective notes and outlines. This chapter will show you how to make the most of these powerful comprehension and retention strategies.
- 06 **Final Assignment** Free

02

Finding the Main Idea Free

Finding and understanding the main idea of a text is an essential reading skill. This chapter will show you how to distinguish the main idea from its support.

- How The Main Idea Works 0 Pages
- Topic Sentence and Where To Find Them 0 Pages
- Main Ideas in Paragraph and Essays 0 Pages
- How Main Ideas Help You Remember 0 Pages
- Conclusion 0 Pages
- Assignment 1 questions

Short Profile

Meet the instructor

Tiara Afdalia

Tiara Afdalia is a student of State Islamic Institute of Palangka Raya, Central Kalimantan, Indonesia. She looks forward to sharing her love of building meaningful and effective content with all students to develop their abilities.

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- ✓ 6 Chapters
- ✓ 1 Certification
- ✓ 50 Questions
- ✓ 1 Video
- ✓ 14 PDF

Become a Strategist

You will learn how to develop, organize and implement a content marketing strategy, analyze and measure the effectiveness of content marketing, write compelling copy, set a strategic framework when writing

Personal brand

You will also learn how to put the ideas presented to you into action and build your own personal brand through content marketing.

LEARNERS

PATH

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FINAL EXAM

Exam 1:29

question 1/20

Medical Practices in Ancient Egypt

Learning from the Dead
To find out why people have died, today's medical examiners perform autopsies (AW-top-seez). They cut open the body and study its parts. Ancient Egyptians also performed autopsies to help understand causes of death. In addition, autopsies helped ancient Egyptians study the human body. By comparing the hearts of people who were different ages, for example, Egyptians could determine what a young, healthy heart was supposed to look like.

Keeping a Written Record
The Egyptians not only studied the human body, but they also kept detailed records of what they discovered. They wrote and drew their observations on papyrus, a form of paper. The papyrus records became the medical textbooks of that time. Their observations allowed Egyptian doctors to share their knowledge, including how to treat various diseases.

Edwin Smith Papyrus
In 1862, an American named Edwin Smith purchased a medical papyrus in Luxor, Egypt. Smith was not a medical expert, but he knew a lot about old documents. He knew that what he had found was valuable. The papyrus turned out to be an ancient textbook on surgery. The papyrus was probably written around 1600 bc, but it was based on information from a thousand years before that. The papyrus presents the information as case studies, including an analysis of how patients survived or died.

Which one best describes what the headings do?

- They tell the main idea of the passage.
- They describe when events happened.
- They tell what each section is mostly about.
- They compare modern and ancient medicine.

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Last Name	Alana

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The Features of User Analytic for Instructors

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Showing 1 of 6 users out of 6

USER	ROLE	REGISTERED ▼	LAST LOGIN	LAST ENROLLM.	STUDY TIME	TOTAL TIME ON PLATFORM	ALL COURSES	COMPL. COURSES	UNCOMPL. COURSES	NOT STARTED	CERTIFICATES	AVG. SCORE	POSTS/ LIKES/ COMMENTS
> Tantri Melania	learner	08-01-2021	08-01-2021	08-01-2021	00:19h	00:19h	1	0	1	0	0	90	0/0/0
> Tasya Alana	learner	06-01-2021	08-01-2021	06-01-2021	00:24h	00:26h	1	1	0	0	1	93	0/0/0
> Riska Dwi Lestari	learner	06-01-2021	06-01-2021	06-01-2021	00:08h	00:08h	1	0	1	0	0	95	0/0/0
> Azizah	learner	06-01-2021	06-01-2021	06-01-2021	00:16h	00:16h	1	0	1	0	0	95	0/0/0
> Muhammad Kausar	learner	04-01-2021	08-01-2021	04-01-2021	00:13h	00:25h	1	0	1	0	0	95	0/0/0

The Features of Exams for Instructors

Gradebook

Export Grades | Export Grades with all tries

Search for a user | Courses: Reading Compre

	Assignment	Assignment	Assignment	Assignment	Quiz	Certificate of C...	Average
Azizah					95		95
Muhammad Kausar	95						95
Riska Dwi Lestari					95		95
Tantri Melania	ungraded	ungraded	ungraded	ungraded	90		90
Tasya Alana	90	90	95	90	100	✓	93
Tiara						✓	

GRADEBOOK

Questionnaire

Save | Import questions | Review

B I U A - x x² A [Rich Text Editor Icons]

QUESTION TITLE

Medical Practices in Ancient Egypt

Learning from the Dead
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Q1(mc): Medical Practices in Ancient Egypt Learning from the Dead To find out why people have died, today's

Q2(mc): Medical Practices in Ancient Egypt Learning from the Dead To find out why people have died, today's

Q3(mc): Medical Practices in Ancient Egypt Learning from the Dead To find out why people have died, today's

Q4(mc): A Diagnosis Every Sunday at exactly 11:00 am, my whole family gathers in the lobby of the Oak Valley Manor for

Q5(mc): A Diagnosis Every Sunday at exactly 11:00 am, my whole family gathers in the lobby of the Oak Valley Manor for

Q6(mc): A Diagnosis Every Sunday at exactly 11:00 am, my whole family gathers in the lobby of the Oak Valley Manor for

Q7(mc): A Diagnosis Every Sunday at

Ask for help

QUESTION BANKS

Assignments

Ungraded | Graded

Search | by Courses: All courses

4 assignments

COURSE	USERNAME	QUESTIONNAIRE	SCORE	DATE
Reading Comprehension	Tantri Melania	Assignment	-	2021-01-08 11:20:09
Reading Comprehension	Tantri Melania	Assignment	-	2021-01-08 11:17:49
Reading Comprehension	Tantri Melania	Assignment	-	2021-01-08 11:13:22
Reading Comprehension	Tantri Melania	Assignment	-	2021-01-08 11:07:47

ASSIGNMENT

Assignments

Ungraded | Graded

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6 assignments

COURSE	USERNAME	QUESTIONNAIRE	SCORE	DATE
Reading Comprehension	Tasya Alana	Assignment	90	2021-01-07 06:01:44
Reading Comprehension	Tasya Alana	Assignment	95	2021-01-07 05:59:34
Reading Comprehension	Tasya Alana	Assignment	90	2021-01-07 05:54:56
Reading Comprehension	Tasya Alana	Assignment	90	2021-01-07 05:49:36
Reading Comprehension	Muhammad Kausar	Assignment	95	2021-01-06 19:53:30
Reading Comprehension	Muhammad Kausar	Assignment	90	2021-01-06 19:10:41

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Events log Export data

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	Tasya Alana	07 Jan 2021 05:47:24	Visited course	Course: Reading Comprehension
	Tasya Alana	06 Jan 2021 23:19:16	Visited course	Course: Reading Comprehension
	Tasya Alana	06 Jan 2021 23:17:21	Visited course	Course: Reading Comprehension
	Tasya Alana	06 Jan 2021 23:16:53	Logged in	Browser: Chrome . Languages: en-us, en . IP: 36.75.65.3 . Country: Indonesia . Region: Kalimantan Tengah . City: Sampit . OS: Windows .
	Tasya Alana	06 Jan 2021 23:16:52	Is a brand new user	
	Azizah	06 Jan 2021 22:04:44	Visited course	Course: Reading Comprehension
	Azizah	06 Jan 2021 21:14:12	Visited course	Course: Reading Comprehension
	Riska Dwi Lestari	06 Jan 2021 21:04:32	Visited course	Course: Reading Comprehension

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EVENTS LOG

Emails log

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27 e-mails

AVATAR	USER	DATETIME	TYPE	SUBJECT
	Tasya Alana	09 Jan 2021 00:00:50	Notification	New message at Language Course
	Tantri Melania	08 Jan 2021 11:04:36	Welcome (to free course)	Welcome to Reading Comprehension
	Tantri Melania	08 Jan 2021 11:04:32	Notification	New message at Language Course
	Tantri Melania	08 Jan 2021 11:04:32	Welcome (after registration)	Welcome to Language Course
	Muhammad Kausar	07 Jan 2021 06:09:39	Notification	New message at Language Course
	Tasya Alana	07 Jan 2021 06:09:27	Notification	New message at Language Course
	Tasya Alana	07 Jan 2021 06:09:18	Notification	New message at Language Course

EMAILS LOG

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THANK YOU

